

**Inclusive Citizenship in
a world in
Transformation:
Co-Designing for
Democracy**

Citizens
Reinventing
Democracy

Inclusive Citizenship in a world in Transformation: Co-Designing for Democracy

Case Studies Interview Guides, applied in the INCITE-DEM case study research

31-07-2024

Authors: Inês Campos e Sandra Oliveira

Grant Agreement 101094258

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority (REA) can be held responsible for them.

Methodological document	Data
Lead Beneficiary	FC.ID
Name	Case Studies Interview guides
Document type:	Methodological Document
Number of Pages	19
Key words	Civic participation, engagement, democratic innovations, narratives, democracy, interviews, case studies
Author:	Inês Campos (FC.ID), Sandra Oliveira (FC.ID)
Contributors	Repo Petteri (UH), Paivi Timonen (UH), Doris Fuchs [WWU], Vanessa Buth [Münster University], Bernd Schlipphak [Münster University], Oliver Treib [Münster University], Eugenio Barchesi (KC), Wander Jager (UG), Lidija Živčič (FOCUS), Erica Löfström [NTNU], David Lamas [TLU], Francesc Cots [ECOU], Jeremie Fosse [ECOU] and Roberto Falanga [ICS]

INCITE-DEM Consortium Partners

Organisation	Type	Country
FCiências.ID - Associação para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Ciências (FC.ID)	Private Non-profit Association	Portugal
University of Münster (WWU)	University	Germany
Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)	University	Norway
University of Groningen (UG)	University	Netherlands
University of Helsinki (UH)	University	Finland
Tallinn University (TLU)	University	Estonia
Instituto de Ciências Sociais -University of Lisbon (ICS)	University	Portugal
Asociacion Eco-Union (ECOU)	Non-Governmental Organisation	Spain
Focus Association for Sustainable Development (FOCUS)	Non-Governmental Organisation	Slovenia
Kyoto Club (KC)	Non-Governmental Organisation	Italy

Contents

1	Introduction	5
2.	Interview Guides	7
2.1	Interview Guide - Citizens	7
2.2	Interview Guide - Policymakers	11
2.3	Interview Guide - Organisers and Other	15

1 Introduction

This document is related to INCITE-DEM Deliverable 2.2 and provides the three guides for the interviews conducted in the context of the INCITE-DEM – Case Study research process.

The comparative case study research of civic participation and engagement, was led by a team from FCIencias.ID (University of Lisbon) and co-lead by Munster University researchers. The work was implemented between May 2023 and January 2024 by the six members of the INCITE-DEM project Consortium that developed the Case Studies (research centres of FC.ID/cE3c, WWU and UH, and civil society organisations FOCUS, KC and ECOU). The aim of this research is to systematically analyse participation and engagement formats, opportunities, and needs in pursuit of socio-ecological transformation, with particular attention to the role of (social) media, the use of public spaces, the role of education for inclusive citizenship, and especially the involvement of vulnerable and disenfranchised communities, seeking to identify determinants of success and failure in these processes.

Thus, 15 case studies of civic participation and engagement in Europe were developed and concluded in more than 10 countries (as three of the Case Studies are transnational, including one documented with interviews from Brazil). The interview process was thoroughly prepared through a set of agreed upon case study guidelines. The three Interview Guides include empirical questions prepared with the collaboration of 15 involved researchers. The researchers brainstorming and discussion process started at INCITE_DEM project Kick-off Meeting in March 2023, based on four overarching research questions:

1. What enabling and hindering conditions are found for inclusive participation and engagement processes?
2. How have critical turning points influenced processes of democratic innovation (either towards an outcome perceived as a success or as a failure)?
3. What was the perceived socio-political output and outcome of democratic innovations?
4. What were the technological contexts for the implementation of democratic innovations?

The empirical questions in these Interview Guides, which emerged from an interdisciplinary research team collaboration, were foreseen to guide the collection of qualitative data on the case studies, and allow an in-depth analysis of the specific key factors and contexts that foster or hinder citizens' participation.

Following the research team's concerns, the three guides were created to suit the targeted interviewees, as each stakeholder may answer and provide inputs to different research questions. The targeted profiles were those of (i) citizens, (ii) policymakers, (iii) organisers and representatives of democratic innovations, and others (eg. facilitators or technical staff).

The guides were used in the 159 semi-structured interviews conducted to ensure comparability in data collection and analysis. Comparability required that each guide included the key questions as well as a set of sub-questions that break down each theme to help the interviewer better explain and be able to harvest the required data from the interviewees. Hitherto the duration of the interviews depended on both the personality and the quantity of information held by each interviewee, ranging from a minimum of 30 minutes to over two and a half hours.

Moreover, Interviewees answered a short socioeconomic factsheet questionnaire that harvested the main demographic, ethnic, education, and subjective economic level data. All data gathering and storage complies with GDPR, and interviewees' data are codified and only accessible to the researchers developing each interview. The ethical procedures of the research interviews are part of the Case Studies Methodological Package where these guides are included, shaping the research process.

Applying these guides to 15 very diverse case studies and the 159 stakeholders interviewed, with a range of age, education, nationality, and socio-economic background diversity, has at the same time tested its usefulness to harvest data in different national and regional contexts. The guides were applied to interview citizens participating in social movements and other grassroots-led initiatives; to policy-makers engaged in capacity-building or collaborative governance processes; to organisers of state-organised participation initiatives or even in the case of an e-participation tool. Hence, these guides support the gathering of the data but equally contribute to harvesting the narratives of individual stakeholders, allowing researchers to take stock of the failures and successes of these initiatives, and to draw a comparative understanding of the factors that shape civic participation and engagement processes, including democratic innovations. In what follows the three guides are presented.

2. INCITE-DEM Interview Guides

2.1 Interview Guide Citizens

Interview Questions

PART I - Enabling and hindering conditions for inclusive participation and engagement

1.1. Why did you join this initiative? Are motivation and incentives important for you? What were some of your personal, political, and/or financial motivations to participate?

1.2. Do you know why this initiative started?

1.3. Who is at the table? And who had what role in the process?
Tell me, if you know:
who were the initiators of the initiative;
Who financed the CS?
who was setting the agenda; and who designed the process;
who was evaluating or monitoring the events/actions/initiatives;
who was communicating or engaged in Public Relations;

1.4. Who invited you, and why?
What were the participants' engagement strategies in place and who invested time in this engagement process? Do you know about the participation of vulnerable people/minorities?

1.5. Who was not invited, or, in your opinion, was missing from the process?
And who disengaged, and dropped out?

I.6 - Did you observe how the events were set up?

Tell me what you know and consider about:

The methodologies needed for the events;

The communication used for the initiative and events;

The technologies or digital frameworks needed for the initiative and events.

I.7 - What were the main benefits and main problems of the initiative?

And what were the benefits and problems of its main events and milestones?

I.8 - How much trust do/did you trust the government (Scale 1-7)? Did this influence your motivation to participate? And how much do/did you trust the organisers (as above)?

I.9 - Was the initiative binding for decision-makers or was it one of consultative nature?

Did this make a difference in your motivation to participate?

I.10 - Are you aware of the decision-making rules and process organisation within the initiative: more of a top-down and hierarchised or an informal and collaborative process?

I.11 - Do/did you feel listened to? Do/did you feel you have some degree of influence in the process? Why?

PART II - Stories, meanings, and community spirit: how critical turning points influenced processes of democratic innovation.

II.1 - Do you see any critical turning points in the initiative?

If yes, tell me if you consider:

The turning point is/was in the events or the context;

There is/was a turning point in the participants;

Or in the initiative direction: a transformative or processual turning point;

II.2 - Do you feel that, throughout the process, your perspective changed? If yes, how has it changed?

In other participants, did you observe a change in their perspective?

If yes, through which aspects or procedures?

II.3 - Did your experience of participation lead to mutual learning or enhanced knowledge?

What would that learning be?

II.4 - Were there any critical conflicts? And how was conflict dealt with? (by participants and by organisers)

II.5 - What did you value the most in this experience?

Can you tell by:

Which moment?

Which element? (e.g. motivations, outcomes, learnings)

Can you illustrate this with a memory, a photo, a video, or a scrapbook?

PART III - Perceived socio-political output and outcome

III.1 - What do you consider the main achievement of the initiative?

Can you tell in terms of:

Environmental achievements;

Social achievements;

Policy achievements;

III.2 - Looking back, how did you receive those results?

Tell me about:

Your reaction at the time of events and achievements?

Your afterthought about those?

And what about other participants: How did political decision-makers, either politicians or officials as policymakers, receive this?

How did the organisers of the initiative receive the results?

How do the audiences and the electorate speak about it?

III.3 - What do you value the most in these results?

Tell me if you have the outcome you wished for?

If yes - is this the most important for you?

Was the process and the way the initiative underwent also important?

And finally, what did you observe in other participants: do they value the results or something else (and what else they value)?

III.4 - Do you know if there is:

Any follow-up next steps for citizens/organisers?

Any binding decision at the policy level?

Any commitment to maintain or develop a new process based on experiences and outputs?

III.5 - Did you feel empowered or heard by this initiative? Was there an opportunity to evaluate and feedback on the experience?

Did the level of transparency and the reporting or feedback make a difference in how you evaluated the process?

III.6 - And who hasn't been empowered or heard?

Do you know why?

How important is it to engage, hear, or empower these people?

III.7 - Do you feel the process enhances a sense of community?

If not, do you feel the process contributes/contributed to a (further) separation between people having different perspectives or interests?

Tell me if there was already a separation in the community (old wounds) before this process; Are there other or more important matters than those currently discussed in the initiative?

PART IV - Technological contexts for the implementation of democratic innovations.

IV.1 - Thinking about the digital technologies used in the process, what were the main advantages and disadvantages?

2.2 Interview Guide Policymakers

Interview Questions

PART I - Enabling and hindering conditions for inclusive participation and engagement

I.1. Why did you join this initiative? What were some of your personal or political motivations to participate?

I.2. Who is at the table? And who had what role in the process?

Tell me, if you know:

who was the initiator of the initiative;

who was setting the agenda;

who designed the process;

who was at the deliberation and decision-making process;

who was evaluating or monitoring the events/actions/initiatives;

Who was communicating or making PR;

Do you know about the participation of vulnerable people/minorities?

I.3. You were invited by whom, and why?

Who was inviting participants and how?

What were the participants' engagement strategies in place and who invested time in this engagement process?

I.4. Who was not invited, or, in your opinion, was missing from the process?

And who disengaged, and dropped out?

I.5 - Did you observe how the events were set up?

Tell me your opinion about:

The methodologies needed for the events;

The communication used for the initiative and events;

The technologies or digital frameworks needed for the initiative and events.

I.6 - What do you find were the main benefits and main weaknesses of the initiative?

I.7 - Was the initiative binding for decision-making or was it one of consultative nature? And how did this frame your participation?

I.8 - How were the decision-making rules and process organisation within the initiative: more of a top-down and hierarchised or an informal and collaborative process?

PART II - Stories, meanings, and community spirit: how critical turning points influenced processes of democratic innovation.

II.1 - Do you see any critical turning points in the initiative?

If yes, tell me if you consider:

The turning point is in the events or the context;

There is a turning point in the participants;

Or in the initiative direction: a transformative or processual turning point;

II.2 - Do you feel that, throughout the process, your perspective changed? If yes, how has it changed?

In other participants, did you observe a change in their perspective?

If yes, through which aspects or procedures?

II.3 - Did your experience of participation lead to mutual learning or enhanced knowledge?

What would that learning be?

II.4 - Were there any critical conflicts? And how was conflict dealt with? (by participants and by organisers)

II.5 - What did you value the most in this experience?

Can you tell by:

Which moment?

Which element? (e.g. motivations, outcomes, learnings)

Can you illustrate this with a memory, a photo, a video, a scrapbook?

PART III - Perceived socio-political output and outcome

III.1 - What do you consider the main achievement of the initiative?

Can you tell in terms of:

Environmental achievements;

Social achievements;

Policy achievements;

III.2 - Looking back, how did you receive the results?

Tell me about:

Your reaction at the time of events and achievements?

Your afterthought about those?

How did the organisers of the initiative receive the results?

How do the audiences and the electorate speak about it?

III.3 - What do you value the most in these results?

Tell me if you have the outcome you wished for.

If yes - is this the most important for you?

Was the process and the way the initiative underwent also important?

And finally, what did you observe in other participants: do they value the results or something else (and what else do they value)?

III.4 - Do you know if there is:

Any follow-up next steps for citizens/organisers?

Any commitment to maintain or develop a new process based on experiences and outputs?

III.5 - Who, in your opinion, hasn't been empowered or heard?

Do you know why?

How important is it to engage, hear, or empower these people?

III.6 - Was there an opportunity to evaluate and feedback on the experience?

Did the level of transparency and of the reporting or feedback make a difference in how you evaluated the experience?

III.7 - Do you consider the process enhanced a sense of community?

If not, do you consider the process contributes to a (further) separation between people having different perspectives or interests?

Tell me if there was already a separation in the community (old wounds) before this process; Are there other or more important matters than those currently discussed in the initiative?

PART IV - Technological contexts for the implementation of democratic innovations.

IV.1 - Thinking about the digital technologies used in the process, what were the main advantages and disadvantages?

2.3 Interview Guide Organisers and Other

Interview Questions

PART I - Enabling and hindering conditions for inclusive participation and engagement

I.1. Why did you organise/facilitate this initiative? What were some of your personal, political, and/or financial motivations to participate?

I.2. What were the institutional and financial conditions for developing the initiative?

The regulatory conditions when you started participating in this initiative;
the normative;
the cultural-cognitive conditions;
Also, what were the financial conditions to organise the initiative?
What were the facilitating and hindering conditions for participation?

I.3. How is the organisers' and the participants' panel structured?

The gender;
the socioeconomic status;
the ethnicity (or other important participants feature).

I.4. Who is at the table? And who had what role in the process?

Tell me, if you know:
who was the initiator of the initiative;
who was setting the agenda;
who designed the process;
who was at the deliberation and decision-making process;
who was evaluating or monitoring the events/actions/initiatives;
Who was communicating or making PR;
Do you know about the participation of vulnerable people/minorities?

I.5. How did you decide who to invite?

What were the participants' engagement strategies in place and who invested time in this engagement process?

I.6. Who, in your opinion, was not invited, or was missing?

And tell me: who disengaged or refused to participate in the process?

I.7 - What was needed to set up the events? Tell me about:

The methodologies needed for the events;

The communication used for the initiative and events;

The technologies or digital frameworks needed for the initiative and events.

I.8 - What were the main benefits/successes and main weaknesses of the initiative?

And what were the benefits and problems of its main events/milestones?

I.9 - Was the initiative binding for decision-making or was it one of consultative nature?

Did this make a difference in your motivation to organise/facilitate the initiative?

I.10 - What were the decision-making rules and process organisation within the initiative: more of a top-down and hierarchised or an informal and collaborative process?

PART II - Stories, meanings, and community spirit: how critical turning points influenced processes of democratic innovation.

II.1 - Do you see any critical turning points in the initiative?

If yes, tell me if you consider:

The turning point is in the events or the context;

There was a turning point in the participants;

Or in the initiative direction: a transformative or processual turning point;

II.2 - Do you feel that, throughout the process, your perspective changed? If yes, how has it changed?
In other participants, did you observe a change in their perspective?
If yes, through which aspects or procedures?

II.3 - Did your experience of participation lead to mutual learning or enhanced knowledge?
What would that learning be?

II.4 - Were there any critical conflicts? And how was conflict dealt with? (by participants and by other organisers, policymakers, etc.)

II.5 - What did you consider the main achievements of the initiative?
Including its most innovative aspects?
Can you tell in terms of:
Environmental achievements;
Social achievements;
Policy achievements.
Can you illustrate this with a memory, a photo, a video, a scrapbook?

PART III - Perceived socio-political output and outcome

III.1 - Looking back, how did you receive the results of the initiative?
Tell me about:
Your reaction at the time of events and achievements?
Your afterthought about those?
And what about other participants: How did political decision-makers, either politicians or officials as policymakers, receive this?

III.2 - Do you know if there is:
Any follow-up next steps?
Any binding decision at the policy level?
Any commitment to maintain or develop a new process based on experiences and outputs?

III.3 - Who do you think was empowered by the initiative and how?

III.4 - And who hasn't been empowered or heard?

Do you know why?

How important is it to engage, hear or empower these people?

III.5 - Was there an opportunity to evaluate and receive feedback on the experience?

Did the level of transparency and the reporting or feedback make a difference in how you evaluated the process?

III.6 - Do you consider the process enhanced a sense of community?

If not, do you consider the process contributes to a (further) separation between people having different perspectives or interests?

Tell me if there was already a separation in the community (old wounds) before this process;

Are there other or more important matters than those discussed in the initiative?

PART IV - Technological contexts for the implementation of democratic innovations.

IV.1 - Thinking about the digital technologies used in the process, what were the main advantages and disadvantages?

incite-dem.eu

facebook.com/InciteDem

twitter.com/InciteDem

linkedin.com/company/incite-dem-citizens-reinventing-democracy